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Preliminary investigations on sandwich panels made of aluminium skins and arch-corrugated core

R T Lopes^{(a), *}, [A J B Campuzano](#)^(b), J C Santos^(c), R T S Freire^(d), F Scarpa^(e), T H Panzera^(f)

(a) 0000-0002-6600-0906 (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(b) 0000-0002-7241-6836 (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(c) 0000-0002-7485-491X (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(d) 0000-0001-5206-5939 (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

(e) 0000-0002-5470-4834 (University of Bristol – United Kingdom)

(f) 0000-0001-7091-456X (Federal University of São João del-Rei – Brazil)

* Corresponding author: rogerioteixeiralopes@gmail.com

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Abstract: Sandwich panels have been widely used in engineering due to their high mechanical strength and stiffness with a low density. The work presents the development and characterisation of a sustainable structural sandwich composite made of recycled aluminium skins bonded to a corrugated arch core obtained by cutting discarded aluminium cans. An epoxy system is used to bond the skins to the core. The structure is tested under a three-point bending test (ASTM C393) to evaluate its potential as a structural material. The sustainable core leads to significant specific mechanical properties, being a promising alternative for recycling discarded cans into an engineered product, adding greater value to waste and contributing to the growth of the circular economy.

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1. Introduction

Due to the increasing exploitation of natural resources, along with their unconscious use by man, there is a worldwide trend of research in engineering and materials science for the creation and feasibility of sustainable construction materials. In this context, in partnership with the academic sector, several segments seek to develop alternative solutions that use light, efficient and low-cost structures, characteristics that can be found in structural sandwich composites [1]. Sandwich structures are made of high-bending stiffness outer skins bonded to low-strength and low-density cores. The main structural features of sandwich composites are their high specific flexural stiffness, strength, and favourable compressive behaviour [2].

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Several core geometries have been developed and evaluated, highlighting Honeycomb and the corrugated cores. The difference between them is in the direction of the cells. According to Bartolozzi *et al* [3], the shape of corrugated core, which has its cells oriented in the same direction as the skins, brings significant benefits to some branches of industry, mainly due to its hollow cavities throughout the structure, allowing the passage of electrical conductors and tubes. Another critical component of the sandwich panel is the adhesive material responsible for keeping the core adhered to the skins. This layer guarantees an efficient skin-core load transfer to maintain the structural integrity of the panel [4].

This work aims to design and characterise a novel sustainable sandwich panel made from recycled aluminium skins and corrugated core composed of arch sections obtained from reused aluminium cans. Both aluminium sheets are tested under tensile loads. An epoxy system is used as an adhesive material, being tested to obtain its mechanical properties.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Composite materials

The sandwich composites are made from recycled aluminium skins bonded to an arch-shaped core produced by cutting up reused aluminium cans. The epoxy system composed of araldite AV 138 and hardener HV 988 is supplied by Huntsman (Brazil). The adhesive is obtained by mixing 10:4 by weight of resin to the catalyst. The polymer density is 1.7 g/cm³ and the curing time is about 48 hours.

Aluminium skins (type ISO 1200 recycled, 0.5 mm thickness) are supplied by *Ibrap* (Brazil). The core material is obtained from discarded aluminium cans from the Ball® manufacturer. The cans are washed and cleaned with conventional detergent to remove residue, then dried at room temperature (approx. 25°C) for 24 hours.

2.2. Fabrication and testing

The first manufacturing step consisted of extracting 25mm wide sections from aluminium cans. A conventional self-producing device such as lathe is used, as shown in Fig. 1a. The bottom of the can is discarded, and subsequent parts are made using an internal curved template to provide structural support for the cutter blade (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1. Manual cutting device filled with internal support: (a) first and (b) second cut.

The arch-shaped core base is obtained by a manual forming process using a 3D printed polymer mould, as shown in Fig. 2. A 12 mm wide transparent adhesive tape is used to keep the straight base together.

Fig. 2. Manufacture of the arched aluminium core.

The sandwich panels are produced using a manual manufacturing process. ISO 1200 type recycled aluminium skins, already cleaned and treated, are inserted into a wooden mould covered by a plastic film to prevent leakage of the adhesive material. The epoxy resin and hardener are mixed and then spread over the aluminium surface located inside the mould (Fig. 3a), creating a uniform adhesive layer weighing 16 grams. Arcs are inserted as shown in Fig. 3b. The mould is closed and a cold press of 2.3 kPa is applied for 24 hours. The same process is repeated for the second skin (Fig. 3c). The specimen size ($213.7 \times 75 \times 14 \text{ mm}^3$) is based on the ASTM C393 standard for long beam samples [5]. The structural outline of the panel is illustrated in Fig. 4. Five samples are produced.

Fig. 3. Manufacture of the sandwich panel: (a) adhesive material on aluminium skin, (b) core inserted after the adhesive material, (c) application of second skin.

The sandwich panels are tested by three-point bending according to ASTM C393 [5]. A span length of 150 mm with a crosshead speed of 4 mm/min is used. The specimens are tested on an INSTRON EMIC 23-100 machine equipped with a 100 kN load cell (Fig. 5). Equivalent density is determined by the ratio between mass and total volume of the sample. The ultimate core shear stress and skin stress are calculated according to ASTM C393 [5], while the flexural stiffness, shear rigidity and core shear modulus are determined according to ASTM D7250 [6]. Specific mechanical properties are determined by dividing the absolute properties by the equivalent density.

In addition, both aluminium sheets, obtained from cans and recycled, are tested under tensile load following ASTM E8 [7] at 2 mm/min. The epoxy polymer is also tested under tensile, compression and three point-bending according to ASTM D638 [8], ASTM D695 [9] and ASTM D790 [10], respectively.

Fig. 4. Structural outline of the sandwich panel

Fig. 5. Three-point bending testing.

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Mechanical results of the panel constituents.

Material	Tensile		Compressive		Bending	
	σ_{max} [MPa]	E_t [GPa]	σ_{max} [MPa]	E_c [GPa]	σ_{max} [MPa]	E_f [GPa]
Aluminium skin	71.04 (\pm 13.3)	35.03 (\pm 1.1)	-	-	-	-
Aluminium core	117.36 (\pm 20.0)	22.89 (\pm 2.2)	-	-	-	-
Adhesive	8.57 (\pm 4.43)	1.99 (\pm 0.2)	49.83 (\pm 5.9)	1.95 (\pm 0.3)	28.90 (\pm 6.4)	3.09 (\pm 0.7)

Table 2. Mean results and standard deviation values of properties obtained during the sandwich flexural tests.

Property	Sandwich panels proposed					Mean values
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	
Equivalent Density (g/cm^3)	0.39	0.36	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.37 (\pm 0.01)
Maximum Load (N)	73.93	64.42	63.05	65.39	72.29	67.82(\pm 4.94)
Flexural Strength (MPa)	1.42	1.34	1.21	1.16	1.39	1.30(\pm 0.11)
Specific Flexural Strength ($N.m.g^{-1}$)	3.64	3.72	3.27	3.14	3.76	3.51(\pm 0.28)
Skin Stress (MPa)	6.16	5.60	5.25	5.23	6.02	5.65(\pm 0.43)
Specific Skin Stress ($N.m.g^{-1}$)	15.80	15.56	14.20	14.14	16.28	15.20(\pm 0.97)
Core Shear Stress (MPa)	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04(\pm 0.01)
Specific Core Shear Stress ($N.m.g^{-1}$)	0.11	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.11	0.10(\pm 0.00)
Core Shear Modulus (MPa)	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.12(\pm 0.00)
Specific Core Shear Modulus ($N.m.g^{-1}$)	0.31	0.33	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32(\pm 0.00)

Table 1 shows the mean values and standard deviation of the mechanical properties of the panel's constituents. Fig. 6 shows the typical stress versus strain curves for aluminium skins and core. A substantial

difference is evidenced between them; while core aluminium achieves higher tensile stress, skin aluminium reaches higher tensile modulus; however, both provide great strain to failure.

Table 2 presents the absolute and specific properties of the panels obtained via a three-point bending test. The presence of hollow cavities throughout the structure makes the panels less rigid, but with a great bending deflection. After the rupture of the adhesive layer at 67.82 N (see Fig. 7), a densification of the core occurs, favouring an increase in toughness. It is noteworthy that these panels will be tested under drop tower impact load in the next step of this research to verify the potential of the arched core to absorb energy.

Fig. 6. Stress-strain of aluminium skin and core.

Fig. 7. Load-displacement of sandwich panel.

4. Conclusions

This work investigated a sustainable sandwich panel composed of recycled aluminium skins and corrugated arched core obtained from reused cans. The tensile properties of aluminium taken from cans are superior to those of recycled aluminium sheets. A three-point bending test is used to characterise the panel properties. The large bending deflections obtained indicated that the arch core configuration may be able to absorb a significant amount of impact energy, being the scope of future investigations. Preliminary results reveal that these panels are promising for secondary structural applications, combining low cost and recyclability and being an alternative route for this material that does not have a well-defined disposal route.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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